

Scientific article

Dispatching wind farm control strategies based on marginal cost pricing

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Abstract: *Wind farm control strategies, such as wake steering, have the potential to significantly improve the energy production of wind farms. However, they also bring risks in the form of elevated loads, which must be traded against the potential upside and settled between multiple parties. Often, this creates a barrier to adopt such technologies, especially in the present volatile markets where energy prices, interest rates, and operating costs are highly uncertain. This paper presents a new practical way to express the fatigue damage of wind farm control through marginal cost. By doing so, a smart dispatch logic is created that switches between several wind farm control strategies based on the day-ahead price.*

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